

MJFF Open Science Policy Guide for Grantees

Purpose and Scope

As The Michael J. Fox Foundation (MJFF) is a public charity, research enabled by funds from MJFF must be conducted in the public interest. We believe that the results of all MJFF-funded research should be promptly published and broadly disseminated to accelerate innovation and foster collaboration toward our shared goal of new treatments and cures for Parkinson's disease. To that end, we have adopted an open science policy for all research that is funded, in whole or in part, by the Foundation, including any publications, underlying data sets, and related code (among other research outputs).

This document constitutes the official MJFF Open Science Policy, itemizing all requirement specifications around policy compliance within our three (3) overarching requirements. Each item within an overarching requirement outlines a specific action that a grantee can take to comply with the Policy and lays the foundation for MJFF to have a consistent compliance monitoring and enforcement workflow. External-facing documentation summarizing the Policy can be found on the [MJFF website](#).

The overarching goal of MJFF's Open Science Policy is for scientific findings that stem from MJFF funding to be accessible, verifiable, and for the associated research outputs to be reusable. Practically speaking, this means that someone looking at a figure panel from an MJFF-funded study should be able to identify and reuse the data that underlie that figure and the code used to analyze that data. The lab protocol and key lab materials used to collect those data are encouraged to be openly shared as well.

This MJFF Open Science Policy Guide is a detailed, external resource for grantees. It largely aligns with, and draws from, the [ASAP guide](#) (Aligning Science Across Parkinson's).¹

This document comes with an accompanying [glossary](#). Glossary terms are linked from the text when they first appear in this document.

This guide will be versioned as policies and guidance are updated over time.

¹ Aligning Science Across Parkinson's. (2025). ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook (December 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17968591>

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Policy Overview

<p>Data*</p> <p>Software and code*</p> <p>Preprints & Articles*</p> <p>Funder acknowledgement</p> <p>Data and code availability statement(s)</p>	<p>Required</p> <p>Required (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Have OA Requirements</p> <p>Required (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Required (<i>new</i>)</p>	<p>Licensing (<i>updated</i>):</p> <p>CC BY is expected for all outputs, or appropriate equivalent in instances where CC BY licenses are not applicable for the given output (e.g., code or software). See the 'Reuse of Research Outputs' section and each specific entry below for additional information.</p>
<p>Materials</p> <p>Pre-registration</p> <p>Protocols</p> <p>RRIDs</p>	<p>Required (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Encouraged (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Encouraged (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Encouraged (<i>new</i>)</p> <p>Encouraged (<i>new</i>)</p>	<p>*Publications must include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Immediate, persistent access ● A PID such as a DOI ● Funder acknowledgement (<i>updated</i>) ● Data and code/software availability statements (<i>new</i>)

Key changes

Updated: CC BY (or equivalent) license for all outputs

Added: Funder acknowledgement, data and software availability statements: *required*
Materials, Pre-registration and Protocols: encouraged, but not required

Summary of Expected Output Availability

- **Data:** Must be made freely available in an established, open repository no later than submission of the first journal manuscript based on the data, *or* a maximum of twelve months following the end of the grant period for grantees, if there is no associated article or preprint.
- **Software & code:** Must be made freely available in an established, open repository no later than submission of the first journal manuscript based on the data *or* a maximum of twelve months following the end of the grant period for grantees if there is no associated article or preprint.
- **Articles:** If you are seeking to publish an article based on research that is funded in whole or in part by MJFF, it must be Open Access (OA) and must be preceded by a preprint (see below). If MJFF-funded research does not result in a publication, you still must share data and code (see above).
- **Preprints:** Strongly Encouraged. If you are seeking to publish a journal article based on research that is funded in whole or in part by MJFF, you must first submit a preprint. In this case, preprints must be submitted no later than the submission of your manuscript to a journal for review. Preprints must be Open Access.
- **Protocols:** Grantees are *encouraged* to make publicly available through a service such as protocols.io.
- **Materials:** See Sharing Policy section of grant agreement for information on making [tools](#) or reagents available.
- **Pre-registration:** Grantees are *encouraged* to pre-register on the Open Science Framework ([OSF](#)).

The MJFF Open Science Policy reflects three (3) main requirements:

1. Sharing of research outputs. By the time of publication (see 2 below) or a maximum of one year embargo for grantees, whichever comes first:

Data and code generated as part of an MJFF-funded study *must* be deposited in a community-recognized repository with accompanying information to facilitate reuse of those outputs and a license that allows for reuse.

MJFF *encourages* sharing of protocols and lab materials (i.e. research inputs) generated as part of an MJFF-funded study, on this same timeline.

2. Ensuring immediate open/public access. Preprints *must* be posted no later than the date a manuscript is submitted to a journal.

Preprints and publications such as journal articles, reports, books/chapters, videos, etc. *must* be immediately publicly available, with a CC BY 4.0 license and include an Availability Statement outlining where all research outputs (Requirement 1, above) can be accessed.

3. Acknowledging MJFF. Research outputs that were partially or fully funded by MJFF *must* acknowledge MJFF.

Date of Implementation

This open science policy took effect on March 15th, 2026. All MJFF grants that enter contracting after this date must comply with this policy. We encourage awardees of active MJFF grants contracted prior to March 15th, 2026 to comply with this policy as well, though they should refer to the terms of their grant for applicable policies at the time their grant award was made. You can also contact your Grants Manager or openscience@michaeljfox.org with any questions.

Policies by Output Types

Publications

Publications Overview		
Articles/other primary outputs	OA Required	License(s): CC BY
Preprints	OA Required	
Must include	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free, immediate, and persistent readership rights ● A PID such as a DOI ● Links to underlying datasets, code, and other outputs relevant to the work ● Funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements, including if none were produced 	

Preprints

Required (CC BY)

If you are seeking to publish a journal article based on research that is funded in whole or in part by MJFF, you *must* first submit a preprint. In this case, preprints must be submitted no later than the submission of your manuscript to a journal for review. Preprints must be open access.

Preprints are strongly *encouraged*, regardless of whether article manuscripts are submitted to journals for publication.

Sharing via personal websites, as permitted in publishing agreements, is permitted but does not on its own meet the criteria for persistent access. To guard against loss of access over time, publications must be shared via institutional and/or dedicated preprint platforms. We consider bioRxiv and medRxiv as preferred repositories, but other community-run or geographic or discipline-specific preprint servers are also acceptable.

All preprints must include:

- Free, immediate and persistent readership rights; AND
- A persistent identifier (PID), such as a DOI (digital object identifier), if available; AND
- Funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements (which link to resources available at time of preprint submission), including if none were produced

If there is not a specified place for Acknowledgements, use the notes or detail area of the record to include funder and grant information:

“This research was funded in whole [replace with “in part” if appropriate] by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF, <https://ror.org/03arq3225>) through grant [insert grant number].”

While we recognize that it is not always feasible to have all outputs available at time of preprint submission, we *recommend* preparing them by that time in the event where it will not materially delay sharing of preprints or submitting manuscripts to journals for review, as it reduces the need for researchers to update preprint submissions and increases the usability of preprints when available. Statements which state that data and/or code are available upon request are not compliant with this policy.

Articles

Required (CC BY)

All publications resulting in whole or in part by MJFF funding support *must* be made available in one of the following formats:

- as a fully open access (OA) article in a fully open access or hybrid open access journal; OR,
- as a preprint or an author’s accepted manuscript (AM or AAM) or equivalent posted to an institutional or subject repository or preprint server with free, immediate and persistent readership rights; OR,
- as a fully public access report, whitepaper, book/chapter, video or other primary output that communicates the results of MJFF-funded research made available on a publisher platform, institutional website or repository, subject repository or preprint server

All articles *must* include:

- Free, immediate and persistent readership rights; AND
- A persistent identifier (PID), such as a DOI (digital object identifier), if available; AND
- Links to underlying datasets, code, and other outputs relevant to the work
- Funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements, including if none were produced

If there is not a specified place for Acknowledgements, use the notes or detail area of the record:

“This research was funded in whole [replace with “in part” if appropriate] by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF, <https://ror.org/03arq3225>) through grant [insert grant number].”

Resources

- FAIR Principles (data): Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
- Lists of preprint servers: [ASAPbio](#), [Directory of Open Access Preprint Repositories](#), [Wikipedia](#)
- Lists of article and other repositories: [Registry of Open Access Repositories](#), [Directory of Open Access Repositories](#), [Confederation of Open Access Repositories](#)

Other Outputs

Required

Other Required Outputs: Overview		
Data (underlying, cleaned)	<i>Required</i>	License(s): CC BY, MIT, GNU GPL, or equivalent
Software and code	<i>Required</i>	
Must include	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Immediate, persistent access ● A PID such as a DOI ● Funder acknowledgement ● Data and code/software availability statements, as applicable 	

Data

Required (CC BY)

Underlying, cleaned

Data *underlying* manuscripts, including those needed for reproducibility and independent verification of research results, *must* be curated, cleaned (see [Glossary](#)) and made freely and publicly available in an established repository no later than:

- Submission of the first journal manuscript based on the data, *or*
- a maximum of one year embargo for grantees, whichever comes first.

In instances when grantees are generating data but no publication is expected, grantees still must deposit curated and cleaned data in an appropriate repository (see the 'Resources for Data' section on the following page for more information).

Data *must* include:

- funder acknowledgement(s);
- software/code availability statement, where applicable, including if no underlying data/code are produced;
- full metadata;

Curation of datasets includes ensuring all contributors are listed, that the metadata about the dataset is accurate and complete, any labels or headers are descriptive, and that the dataset is stored in a repository that assigns a persistent identifier such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or accession number. When possible, datasets should include a version number.

Cleaned data are the data entered into an analysis script and may represent the individual data points displayed in figures. The amount of preprocessing and cleaning that occurs will vary greatly depending on the data type. Cleaned data are often in tabular format and can be uploaded to generalist data repositories like Zenodo.

We *recommend* that awardees inform MJFF staff either during their grant review check-ins or earlier where feasible (by contacting your Grant Manager or openscience@michaeljfox.org) that they are in the process of preparing data for sharing so that MJFF staff can assist with any questions and ensure timely sharing and accurate preparation of such outputs.

Data sharing terms in grant agreements may supersede this policy.

Resources for Data

MJFF expects grantees to deposit data in appropriate public or controlled-access repositories. We have developed [additional guidance on recommended repositories](#) for data deposition based on common data types generated through MJFF-funded research. These repositories reflect widely accepted community standards and may be appropriate for many projects. However, grantees are not limited to these options. If another repository better fits your data type, community standards, or governance requirements, please consult MJFF to ensure alignment with open science expectations prior to data deposition.

Grantees should review repository submission requirements early in the project lifecycle to ensure alignment with consent language, governance obligations, and metadata standards. Grantees must ensure that participant consent permits deposition and that required study-, subject-, and sample-level metadata are submitted.

Additional Resources:

- Lists of data repositories/types: [NIH-supported repositories](#) (includes general repositories such as [Dryad](#) and [Zenodo](#) as well as domain-specific options such as [NCBI](#), generalist repositories such as Dryad and Zenodo, disciplinary and specialist repositories, and government repositories such as NCBI).
- For best practices in data curation for repository deposit, review your chosen repository's guidance, or see the Data Curation Network's [CURATE\(D\) checklists](#).
- For anonymizing sensitive data, please refer to local legislation. Some U.S.-based examples can be found via the [NIH](#) or [HHS](#). European colleagues can refer to [GDPR](#).
- For colleagues working with PD data (generated by MJFF or otherwise), we suggest joining [MJFF's Data Community of Practice](#) to connect with colleagues and troubleshoot problems.

Sensitive Data

Required (CC BY)

Where possible, sensitive data (see [Glossary](#)) *must* be curated (e.g. an appropriate degree of anonymization) for open sharing to the extent permitted through research ethics approval. If necessary, it can be shared with controlled access, which *must* include instructions for requesting access.

Sensitive data include data that contain personal information, such as protected health information, and any other data that is likely to negatively harm an individual or community if publicly released. Please refer to local regulations governing data anonymization best practices.

Software and Code

Required (MIT, GNU GPL or Equivalent)

Any code or software created for or during the research process that is beneficial for independent verification of research results *must* be curated for reuse, with funder acknowledgement(s) and a data availability statement, where applicable, and made freely and publicly available in an established, open repository no later than the submission of the first journal manuscript based on the data or a maximum of twelve months following the end of the grant period for grantees, if there is no associated preprint or paper.

Code and software *must* be made available under the MIT License, GNU General Public License or equivalent, unless code and software development is done in conjunction with an existing open-source software project having an alternative preferred license.

⚠ Note that citing a GitHub URL alone is not sufficient because the content is not preserved and can be removed.

If no code was generated, this *must* be included in the Availability Statement. We *recommend* using the following language:

“No code was generated for this study; all data cleaning, preprocessing, analysis, and visualization was performed using [insert program name(s)].”

Resources for Code

- Code must be shared through a repository designed for codesharing. GitHub is a popular option, including [the repository](#) maintained by MJFF’s Data Community of Practice, but other open repositories are permitted. Zenodo is another popular option for sharing code.
- DOIs must be assigned and provided alongside code, which can be done through the open repository [Zenodo](#), even if the code is hosted elsewhere.
- Guidance on choosing a software repository from the [Software Sustainability Institute](#) and International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility ([INCF](#))
- [FAIR4RS](#) Principles (research software)

Other Outputs

Encouraged

Other Encouraged Outputs: Overview		
Materials Pre-registration Protocols	Encouraged Encouraged Encouraged	License(s): CC BY, for all outputs
Include as best practice:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Immediate, persistent access ● A PID such as a DOI ● Funder acknowledgement ● Data and code/software availability statements, as applicable 	

Materials

Encouraged (Grant-Specific, CC BY)

Tools or reagents, including cell lines, transgenic models, plasmids/clones, and antibodies, that are funded in whole or in part by MJFF should be made readily available to the community and citable, with funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements, where applicable, as a means of supporting reproducibility and enabling further research.

In certain cases, MJFF may mandate sharing through the MJFF Sponsored Tools, which provides recommendations for [where to deposit tools](#), or with an MJFF-identified repository.

Sharing Policy of the MJFF grant agreement describes the mechanism by which the tools or reagents should be made available to the research community.

Pre-Registration Access

Encouraged (CC BY)

Pre-registration is “the process of formally documenting essential information about a research study. The goal is to establish a clear, predetermined research

plan while enhancing the credibility of the scientific process.” –Center for Open Science

MJFF grantees are *encouraged* to pre-register on the Open Science Framework (OSF), with funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements, where applicable, prior to first publication:

<https://help.osf.io/article/601-registration-overview>

Protocols

Encouraged (CC BY)

Experimental protocols that are employed in published MJFF-funded research should be made publicly available (and updated as needed), with funder acknowledgement(s) and data and software/code availability statements, where applicable, through a protocol-sharing service such as protocols.io. For information on preparing protocols for submission to protocols.io or another repository, we suggest reviewing [the following guidance](#).

Additional Guidance

Additional information, examples and resources on policy topics organized in alphabetical order.

Acknowledgements

Required

Availability statement. Preprints and Publications *must* include an Availability Statement (see [glossary](#)) outlining where all of the underlying data and code/software can be accessed. Grantees are encouraged to include availability of protocols and key lab materials as well.

Where underlying data or code/software were not produced, the availability statement should still be included, indicating no such resources were created.

While we recognize that it is not always feasible to have all outputs available at time of preprint submission, we *recommend* preparing them by that time in the event where it will not materially delay sharing of preprints or submitting manuscripts to journals for review, as it reduces the need for researchers to

update preprint submissions and increases the usability of preprints when available. Statements which state that data and/or code are available upon request are not compliant with this policy.

MJFF *must* be acknowledged as a source of funding for all deposited data, code, protocols, and key lab materials. This applies regardless of whether data, code, protocols, and key lab materials are deposited or registered during the funding period or after the funding period has ended.

Zenodo and protocols.io have specific fields where the funder (MJFF) and the associated grant number(s) can be listed.

For GitHub repositories, preprint servers, journals, or repositories which do not have a specified place for Acknowledgements, use the README, notes, or detail area of the record to include funder and grant information as follows:

“This research was funded in whole [replace with “in part” if appropriate] by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF, <https://ror.org/03arq3225>) through grant [insert grant number].”

Code and Software

Required

Any code or software created for or during the research process that is beneficial for independent verification of research results *must* be curated for reuse, with funder acknowledgement(s) and a data availability statement, where applicable, and made freely and publicly available in an established, open repository no later than the publication of the first paper based on the data or no later than one year after the end of the grant period for grantees in the event that there is no associated preprint or paper, whichever comes first.

Figure 1. Schematic of the terminology created by ASAP regarding code. We use the term *code* to encompass all software, programs, packages, and scripts. We use *software* to indicate code that was written for reuse by others, and *scripts* to indicate code that was primarily written to clean and analyze the data from a particular study.

See the [glossary](#) for specific definitions.

⚠ Availability Statements that state that data and/or code/software are available upon request are not sufficient.

Programs (e.g., GraphPad Prism, ImageJ; see [glossary](#)). All programs used in a study *must* be unambiguously identified. The manuscript *must* include (1) the program version number, if one exists, (2) the program name, and (3) a URL, DOI, or persistent identifier where information about the program can be found.

Discipline-specific packages (see [glossary](#)). For all discipline-specific packages, the manuscript *must* include (1) the version number, if one exists, (2) the package name, and (3) a URL where information about the package can be found.

Generalist packages (see [glossary](#)). We do not require that generalist packages are listed in the manuscript or KRT. They *must* be listed alongside the deposited code. They must include at least (1) the version number, and (2) the package name.

We *recommend* depositing code in a GitHub repository (such as [MJFF's](#)) and then issuing a persistent identifier (e.g., a DOI) to the repository using Zenodo (instructions [here](#)) and citing that DOI in the manuscript, though depositing code elsewhere and generating DOIs by other methods is permitted. We *require* that manuscripts cite a persistent identifier to the code as it was run for that study. We also *recommend* citing the GitHub URL, so that a reader can access any updates that were made to the code, however, citing a GitHub URL alone is *not sufficient* because the content is not preserved and can be removed.

Analyses without code. When data cleaning, analysis, and/or visualization was conducted without coding scripts (e.g., they were performed using GraphPad Prism or another software with a graphical user interface that does not output a script), we *recommend* that grantees include a detailed and unambiguous explanation of how the cleaning, analysis, and/or visualization was performed. We recommend sharing files (e.g., Prism files), screenshots of images or videos, step-by-step written instructions of the actions performed, and/or any other relevant material. This could be done in a separate document with an itemized explanation for how each panel figure was produced as well as the steps taken to clean and preprocess the data.

Readme file (code). Each code deposit *must* include a readme file entitled "README". Readme files *must* include enough information that someone who was not part of the study team can access the code, identify which scripts execute which functions (e.g., clean data, produce figures), and understand the scripts well enough to reuse them. [Further guidance](#) is available from ASAP.

Computational environment. Code deposits *must* include a file that lists the session information, packages and their version numbers, and any other information needed to recreate the computational environment in which the code was run. This item can be met in several ways. For example, by using packages like ‘sessioninfo’ and ‘renv’ in R, a jupyter notebook, or a dockerfile.

Additional Recommendations

Code commenting. We *encourage* code comments throughout so that someone reading the code can easily understand what the code is doing. This can also be achieved by including explanatory text in a Jupyter notebook or markdown file.

Reproducible container. This allows the code to be run without needing to download materials or install software or packages. This can be achieved using a website like codeocean.com or a Jupyter notebook.

RRIDs (software). We *encourage* including RRIDs for all programs and discipline-specific packages. RRIDs can be found by searching [SciCrunch](https://scicrunch.org).

Cost Coverage

MJFF shall pay reasonable fees required by a publisher to effect publication on these terms, which can include costs not included in the original grant (usually article processing charges (APCs); note that color charges are not allowable charges), for one year after grant end date. Requests for open access funding must be made prior to grantee payment of fees to the publisher.

For more information on this process, please visit; <https://www.michaeljfox.org/request-article-processing-charge-apc-funds>.

Data

Access instructions

If the data are not openly available (i.e., in the event that data sharing terms in an applicable grant supersede this policy), the article or preprint must include information on how a reader can access the data and who they would need to contact to request access.

Repositories

Data must be deposited in the format accepted by a community-recognized repository.

Discipline-specific repositories are designed to hold specific data types (e.g., [CRN Cloud](#), [GEO](#), [SRA](#)); and are in contrast to generalist repositories that can hold all data types (e.g., [Zenodo](#), [Dryad](#)). Please see the ‘Resources for Data’ section on Page 10 of this document, as well as the [additional guidance on recommended repositories](#) for data deposition that we have developed based on common data types generated through MJFF-funded research.

Curation

Curation of datasets includes ensuring all contributors are listed, that the metadata about the dataset is accurate and complete, any labels or headers are descriptive, and that the dataset is stored in a repository that assigns a persistent identifier such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or accession number.

Deposited data *must* come with:

- a CC BY license;
- a persistent identifier (e.g., a Digital Object Identifier–DOI) that is cited in the manuscript, if applicable;
- a readme file entitled “README”
 - Readme files *must* include enough information so that someone who was not part of the study team can access the data, identify which data produce which results (e.g., figure panels), and understand the data well enough to reuse them. ASAP provides additional [guidance on README files](#).
 - If a repository does not allow readme files, include the equivalent information in the appropriate metadata fields.

When possible, datasets should include a version number.

Clean(ed) data (see [glossary](#)) are the data entered into an analysis script and may represent the individual data points displayed in figures. Cleaned data used to produce all results, including figure panels, tables, graphs, and numbers presented in the results section of a manuscript *must* be deposited in a publicly accessible repository. This includes image quantification data. Cleaned data are often in tabular format and have often been preprocessed. It is possible, but unlikely, that the raw data and cleaned data will be the exact same.

 Datasets that include only summary data (e.g., means, standard deviations—see [glossary](#)) can be shared, but are not sufficient to meet this policy item.

Citation

Persistent identifiers. All data used in a study—but which were not generated as part of the study—*must* be cited using a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI or accession number).

If a persistent identifier does not exist for the dataset being used, please include a link to the repository webpage, release number (if applicable), and the date accessed.

Portion of data used. We *recommend* you state the portion of the data used in your study (e.g., which participants, which variables).

Additional Recommendations

Formatting of tabular data. For data types that are stored in tabular format, the data should be deposited as a .csv file or another plaintext, non-proprietary equivalent (e.g., .txt, .tsv). All the data should be contained within text. Color coding and text formatting are not retained in .csv files and are not best practice for data management. We recommend each column represents a single variable and each row represents a single unit of observation. We also recommend including a data dictionary that explains each variable. Additional [guidance on tabular data](#) is available from ASAP.

Folder and file structure. For types of data where a standard community-accepted file structure, folder structure, and/or specification exist, we recommend grantees use that structure or specification, e.g. the [Brain Imaging Data Structure \(BIDS\)](#) for neuroimaging data.

Licenses

Code reuse license. Code *must* be deposited with a license that allows reuse. We *recommend* [the MIT License](#) (or another permissive license). Copyleft licenses are also allowed (e.g., [GNU General Public License](#)).

Materials

Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) are *encouraged* for:

- The following newly-generated organisms: mouse, rat, zebrafish, and Drosophila using this [form](#). Guidance for registering these novel organisms is located in the [SciCrunch Resource Citation Guidelines](#)

- Newly-generated stable cell lines, including those that have been engineered with CRISPR/Cas9, Zinc Finger Nucleases, and Transcription Activator-like Effector Nucleases (TALEN) gene-editing processes. We recommend registering cell lines at Cellosaurus by emailing cellosaurus@sib.swiss
- Newly-generated plasmids at [Addgene](https://www.addgene.org/). Addgene plasmids are registered RRID items in the format of RRID:Addgene_####. See <https://www.addgene.org/deposit> for more information
- Newly-generated antibodies may be registered at the [Antibody Registry](https://www.antibodyregistry.org/)
- Open Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs). We *recommend* that the MTA associated with newly-generated key lab materials is open. A [template Open MTA](#) is available from biobricks

If an RRID does not exist, the manuscript *should* explicitly state that an RRID does not exist.

Shared materials. Grantees are *encouraged* to include source information for key lab materials that were shared (e.g., material name, donor lab, and donor institution). We recommend that grantees discuss registering these materials with the donor lab, but recognize that this may be outside a grantee's control to do.

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

DOIs

Publication DOI in preprint. Upon having a manuscript accepted for publication and receiving a DOI, grantees should add the publication DOI to the preprint. bioRxiv and medRxiv generally make this link automatically.

ORCIDs

ORCIDs are required by MJFF's grant management system, SmartSimple, and are *encouraged* for use with all outputs. Additionally, grantees are *encouraged* to enable '[auto update](#)' in their ORCID profiles, which allows DOI registration agencies like Crossref and DataCite to automatically add new outputs and updates to existing ones to ORCID profiles.

Protocols

Published protocols (see [glossary](#)). For all protocols mentioned in a manuscript where recipe-style instructions already exist (i.e., published protocols), the

manuscript *must* include (i) a DOI to the protocol, (ii) an explanation of what steps of the protocol were followed (this could be a statement that all steps were followed), and (iii) whether any modifications were made, and if so, what those modifications are (this could be a statement that no modifications were made). If a grantee made substantial modifications to a protocol, we *recommend* they [fork the protocol](#) (if it already exists on protocols.io) or publish a new protocol.

Unpublished protocols. For all protocols that are mentioned in a manuscript but are not cited with a persistent identifier that links to recipe-style instructions (see [glossary](#)), we *encourage* grantees to create a recipe-style protocol, deposit the protocol to receive a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) (e.g. using [protocols.io](#)), and cite the persistent identifier in the manuscript. See the [glossary](#) for a detailed explanation of published versus unpublished protocols. Additional [protocols guidance](#) is available from ASAP.

Exception: We consider *in silico* methods to be code

Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs)

Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) are persistent, unique ID numbers assigned to help researchers cite key resources (antibodies, model organisms and software projects) in the biomedical literature to improve transparency of research methods.

To learn more about RRIDs, please visit: <https://www.rrids.org/>.

(Appendix A: FAQs & Additional Information follows on next page).

Appendix A: FAQs/Additional Information

- **When should I post a preprint?**

Preprints must be posted no later than the date a manuscript is submitted to a journal.

- **What if my project doesn't (or isn't intended to) result in either a preprint or an article?**

We recognize that not all projects will result in a preprint or in a journal article. That said, we still think it critical to share other research outputs generated in the course of your research project and so requirements for return/deposit of outputs remain. Please refer to the 'Data' and 'Software and Code' sections above which dictate timelines for public sharing of those outputs. If you subsequently decide to publish a preprint and/or article based on MJFF funded research, the requirements outlined in this policy remain in effect.

- **What if I am an awardee of an ASAP-funded grant?**

Please refer to your grant's and/or study's terms (i.e., data use agreement and/or publication policy). ASAP-funded grants will continue to be governed by the ASAP open science policy, which can be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13769765>. Studies supported by ASAP, such as PPMI, are also governed by ASAP policies. For questions, please refer to the contact email below.

- **What is meant by public access? How is it different from open access?**

The US White House Office of Science and Technology Policy says: "OSTP and federal agencies draw distinctions between the terms public access and open access. Public access refers to the free availability of federally funded scholarly materials to the public (including publications, data, and other research outputs) and is a policy term; whereas, open access refers to a broad set of publication sharing principles and practices, including those required by public access, as

adopted by the scientific and publishing communities.”² UNESCO defines open access as: Open Access means free access to scientific information and unrestricted use of electronic data for everyone.”³

- **How do I determine appropriate repositories?**

Repositories should be open and ideally provide persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). Each section above provides links to choosing repositories appropriate to each output type. Several repositories, such as Zenodo (and others to be confirmed), enable depositors to mint DOIs free of charge upon submission of their research outputs.

- **Do I have to do the curation for sharing data, software and code?**

See above sections on Data Access and Sensitive Data. Curation, to enable replication of results, is required for the former type of data. Basic curation best practices include ensuring that the metadata (title, contributors, affiliations, and persistent identifier) are all complete, that the dataset has clear headers or annotation, and that software or code are documented and have a README file.

- **What if I still have questions?**

For questions, please contact: openscience@michaeljfox.org.

(Appendix B: Glossary follows on next page).

² Office of Science and Technology Policy. (2022, August). *Economic Landscape of Federal Public Access Policy* <https://bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov/ostp/news-updates/2022/08/31/economic-landscape-of-federal-public-access-policy/>

³ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-access>

Appendix B: Glossary

Policy Levels

The MJFF Open Science Policy uses three specific terms to describe the policy items: *Required*, *Encouraged*, and *Exception*. Each of those terms has a specific definition which are defined below.

Required

If a *required* item is not met, we consider the related output (e.g., publication, data deposit) to be non-compliant with the Policy. Each *required* item comes with a workflow that the MJFF Open Science team employs to assess whether the item has been met.

In relevant documents, we may also use the terms *must* or *ensure* to indicate that an item is required. For example, “to make this output compliant, a researcher *must...*” or “We ask that researchers *ensure* that...”.

Encouraged

Items that are *encouraged* can be thought of as items that MJFF considers as nice-to-have. These are intended to promote aspirational practices and/or additional activities that more richly support open, reproducible science.

Exception

Exceptions indicate specific conditions where a *required* item does not need to be fully met for an output to be compliant with the Policy; or when an item that is *not required* must be addressed to be compliant with the Policy.

Data

Cleaned Data

Cleaned data are the data entered into an analysis script and may represent the individual data points displayed in figures. Cleaned data originate from raw data. The amount of preprocessing and cleaning that occurs will vary greatly depending on the data type. Cleaned data are often in tabular format and can be uploaded to generalist data repositories like Zenodo. Some discipline-specific repositories may also allow cleaned data to be deposited alongside raw data.

Cleaned data are not the same as *summary data* (see below). For the purposes of the MJFF Open Science Policy, in the context of image quantification, we consider the image files to be the raw data, and the image quantification to be the cleaned data.

Some researchers in the life sciences also use the term *source data* or *processed data* to describe what we are calling cleaned data.

Curated Data

Curation of datasets includes ensuring all contributors are listed, that the metadata about the dataset is accurate and complete, any labels or headers are descriptive, and that the dataset is stored in a repository that assigns a persistent identifier such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or accession number. When possible, datasets should include a version number.

Summary Data

We define *summary data* as the data that summarize more than one observation (e.g., means, standard deviation). These values may appear in figures and tables or as other numbers in the results section of a manuscript. Sharing these data can be useful, because the exact numbers are not always visible in figures. We consider *summary data* to be the output of a statistical analysis, and *cleaned data* to be the input of that statistical analysis.

Sensitive Data

Sensitive data include data that contain personal information, such as protected health information, and any other data that is likely to negatively harm an individual or community if publicly released.

Open Data

Definition from [data.bris](#): Open data is the most permissive data access level and is used for data which has no particular sensitivities. Where research participants are involved, they have given consent to share anonymised data as 'Open' data; the risk of re-identification of participants is considered to be extremely low. Open data is released under a re-use license.

Restricted Data

Definition from [data.bris](#): Restricted data has some degree of sensitivity involved. For example, research participants have not given explicit consent to share data as Open data. However, the risk of re-identification of participants is considered low. Data is made available to approved bona fide researchers only, after their host institution has signed a Data Access Agreement.

Controlled Data

Definition from [data.bris](#): Controlled data has a large degree of sensitivity involved. For example, research participants have not given explicit consent to share as Open data and/or the risk of re-identification of participants is medium to high. Requests for Controlled data are referred to an appropriate Data Access Committee for approval before data can be shared with bona fide researchers, after their host institution has signed a Data Access Agreement.

Note, after depositing restricted or controlled data, it is not the researcher who collected the data who decides who gets access, it is the organization that manages the data that makes these decisions

Quality Control (QC) Data / Confirmatory Data / Intermediate Data

The data collected to ensure the reliability, accuracy, and consistency of experimental results. This includes measurements and checks performed to validate sample integrity, instrument performance, and procedural accuracy. These data are used to identify and correct errors and to ensure that the data are trustworthy. Confirmatory data include many assays, such as chromatography, genotyping, and confirmatory sequencing. Intermediate data are produced part way through the process of converting raw data to cleaned data.

Code and Software

Scripts

These include all code that a researcher wrote to clean, curate, preprocess, analyze, visualize, or manipulate data in any way. We opt for the term script as opposed to 'code' to describe this because it may reduce ambiguity with the more broad use of code.

Software

We use this term to describe code that was written with the intention to be used more than once. For example, software may be maintained and designed to be used by others who were not involved in writing the software. Software includes both programs / commercial / consumer software (complete and executable) and packages (which extend the functionalities of programs). We discuss software in terms of (i) programs, (ii) discipline-specific packages, and (iii) generalist packages (defined below).

Program

Software that is made by a company, open source community, or individual that is executable on its own. The software is designed to be used by others and may include a Graphical User Interface—GUI. For example: GraphPad Prism, ImageJ, Fiji, R, Python, Matlab, STAR (Spliced Transcripts Alignment), FastQC, SAMtools.

Discipline-specific Package

Packages are collections of code that developers have written to add specific functionalities to programs like R, Python, and Matlab. If the package serves a specific scientific purpose, we call that a *discipline-specific package*. For example: MetaPhlan 3.0, AccuSleep, MERINGUE, Slingshot.

Generalist Package

These are packages that were not designed for a specific scientific discipline. For example, the package *tidyverse* was made to make coding more streamlined and *ggplot* was made to plot various types of data. For example: dplyr, ggplot, tidyverse, kable, numpy, pandas.

Protocols

Recipe-style Instructions

We define recipe-style instructions as clearly written documentation on how to perform a particular protocol, procedure, methodology, or technique. Recipe-style instructions will often include a list of all the lab materials required and a step-by-step explanation of what to do. We only consider documents where the writing is specifically directed toward a reader who is trying to repeat that protocol to be recipe-style instructions. Guidance is available from [ASAP](#).

Published Protocol

We consider a protocol to be published if an identifier (e.g., DOI, URL) exists that brings a reader to *recipe-style instructions*. Published protocols can include:

- Protocols on repositories like protocols.io.
- Protocol articles or methods articles (e.g., articles in journals like *STAR Protocols* and *Nature Methods*).
- Manufacturers' instructions.
- Outsourced procedures.

Note, if you cannot provide an identifier that a reader can follow and arrive at recipe-style instructions for any of the four types of protocols listed above, then we consider them *unpublished protocols*.

Unpublished Protocol

We consider a protocol to be unpublished if there is not an identifier that can bring a reader to *recipe-style instructions*. Unpublished protocols can include:

- Protocols that your team developed, but have not yet deposited to a repository like protocols.io.
- Methods outlined in regular research articles.
- Protocols that were developed based on a published protocol, but contain substantial modifications (i.e., where it would be easier to write a new or [“forked” protocol](#), rather than list every modification).
- Protocols with several steps, even when some of those steps are to follow a specific manufacturer’s instructions.
- Outsourced procedures.

Forked Protocol

On [protocols.io](#), there is an option to “fork” a protocol. This allows a user to copy a published protocol, edit the text, and then publish a modified version of the protocol that will be linked to the original version of protocol. We encourage forking because it provides a clear link to the original protocol.

Additional Terms

Outputs

NISO (The National Information Standards Organization, US) defines [“Scholarly output”](#) as:

A product created or executed by scholars and investigators in the course of their academic and/or research efforts. Scholarly output may include but is not limited to journal articles, conference proceedings, books and book chapters, reports, theses and dissertations, edited volumes, working papers, scholarly editions, oral presentations, performances, artifacts, exhibitions, online events, software and multimedia, composition, designs, online publications, and other forms of intellectual property. The term scholarly output is sometimes used synonymously with research outputs.

Note that this definition does not include data, which is a focus of MJFF’s policy.

Further, MJFF agrees with [The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) that outputs may or may not be tied to publications.

Key Lab Materials

Key lab materials include organisms, cell lines, plasmids, viruses, and antibodies. MJFF's Open Science Policy requires that manuscripts report RRIDs when available for key lab materials. Other lab materials include kits, reagents, hardware, and primers.

Availability Statement

We use the term Availability Statement broadly to encompass any and all sections of a manuscript that appear under a header that is specifically related to the availability of data, code, protocols, and/or lab materials. These section headers could be: Data Availability, Data and Code Availability, Materials Availability, Resource Availability, Open Science Practices, or contain other relevant terms.

For example, the journal *Cell* requires both a Data and Code Availability Statement and a Materials Availability Statement. We use the term *Availability Statement* to encompass both of these manuscript sections.

MJFF-funded Work

MJFF funds are project-based, meaning they are given to each team based on the work they proposed. MJFF-funded work should relate to the team's proposed project and consists of any of the following:

- Projects that are listed in the MJFF-funded proposal
- Methods or resource papers that enable the MJFF-funded proposal
- Pivots stemming from the findings of the MJFF-funded proposal
- Thought leadership pieces (reviews, communications, letters) on the topic that the MJFF-funded proposal aims to address

Manuscript

We use the term manuscript to refer to a document reporting a research study. This definition includes all of the following: a draft that is not yet publicly shared, a preprint, a publication.

Original Research

We define original research as any piece of research that includes the collection of new data or a formal analysis of existing data. Original research is subject to all items in the MJFF Open Science Policy. Non-original research includes reviews, communications, letters, and thought leadership pieces that do not include the collection of new data nor a formal analysis of existing data.

For questions, please contact: openscience@michaeljfox.org.